

QUIZ**LAST NAME: PULCHAN****FIRST NAME: CANDICE****PROGRAM CODE: PHGH****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.
The author used Turabian (footnotes)
The author used Zotero to insert references
The author used the following software: MSWord 2010 on Windows 10)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. **When documenting research the purpose of a style guide is to :**
 - Facilitate the ability to follow a Standard English writing style as an innate quality for any writer.
 - To express the personal style of the author.
 - Provide a means of documenting basic rules or features of your writing that will allow you to ensure consistency in your written output.¹**
 - Only ensure the correct usage of punctuation, grammar, and vocabulary.

2. **In a good academic essay the author must :**
 - Write everything he/she knows about the topic.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, eds., *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 2nd ed. (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019), 24.

- Include a range of information and viewpoints from different authors that explore the key arguments and relevant aspects of a particular topic.²**
 - Represent the data analyzed only from his/her viewpoint.
 - Only include evidence that agrees with his/her argument.
3. **Which of the following is the best way to evaluate the reliability of an online source of information:**
- Site is well maintained and supported by a single individual.
 - The site passionately advocates for or against a social issue.
 - The site is listed on the first page of a Google search.
 - Trust a site only if scholarly readers would trust who maintain it.³**
4. **Citation styles may differ greatly but their aim is to:**
- Give readers the information they need to identify and find a source.⁴**
 - Show readers the research tradition that informs your work.
 - Give credit and recognition to the source of information.
 - To avoid plagiarism.
5. **In Turabian author-date citation style, how should unpublished sources be quoted in a reference list?**

² Cleenewerck and Gulma, 2.

³ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 8th ed., rev. Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Chicago Guides to Writing, Editing, and Publishing (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 29.

⁴ Turabian, 87.

- Roman type, enclosed in quotation marks.**⁵
- They should not be cited at all.
- Roman type enclosed in quotation marks and italicized.
- Capitalized and enclosed in brackets.
6. **Which of the following statements is correct?**
- Research problem follows research approach.
- A research problem should be modified to fit a research approach.
- Research approach follows research problem.**⁶
- Regardless of your research question, you can assume a particular qualitative approach.
7. **With regard to literature reviews in the qualitative research , which of the following statement is correct?**
- In a phenomenological study the literature is reviewed primarily following data collection.**⁷
- In a phenomenological study the literature is reviewed before data collection.
- In grounded theory, the main literature review is conducted before data collection.
- In an ethnographic study, the literature is reviewed after the data is collected.

⁵ Turabian, 150.

⁶ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: Sage Publications, 2008), 7.

⁷ Bloomberg and Volpe, 47.

8. **Which of the following terms best defines methodology :**

- Methodology commonly denotes the specific techniques, procedures, or tools used to generate data.
- Methodology refers to how research proceeds and encompasses a range of logistical, relational, ethical and credibility issues.⁸**
- Methodology provides the theoretical grounding for the research study.
- Methodology is used to describe how the data collection instruments you have chosen are appropriate to the study.

9. **In qualitative research, fore-understanding, interrogation and reflection represent the three distinctive phases of which of the following tradition of inquiry?**

- Grounded Theory.
- Ethnography.
- Hermeneutics.
- Interpretive phenomenology.⁹**

10. **In public health ecological studies are useful since they :**

- Inform about variability of factors and interrelated determinants in groups rather than individuals.¹⁰**
- Describe the interactive process between an individual and his environment.

⁸ Bloomberg and Volpe, 73.

⁹ Koya Allen, "Cultural Embeddedness & the International Traveler," (PhD diss., Kent State University College of Public Health, 2013), 59.

¹⁰ Adriana del Pilar Pacheco-Coral, "The role of migration processes in dengue fever occurrence in Columbia: a mixed study approach," (PhD diss., University College London, 2016), 118.

- Compares research outcomes among individuals in a specific niche.
- Determine the impact of human interactions in a particular ecosystem.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.